

FRANCE

FRANCE

DEMOKRATIK JAMIYATDA SAYLOVNING AHAMIYATI

Nusratillayev Ziyodbek G'ayrat o'g'li

Namangan davlat universiteti Yuridik fakulteti 1-bosqich talabasi

<https://doi.org/>

Abstract:

Keywords: demokratiya, saylov, fuqarolik jamiyati, inson huquqlari, konstitutsiya, siyosiy islohotlar, saylov tizimi

References:

1. Toshbekov N.A. Kollektor-drenaj suvlaridan foydalanish imkoniyatlari. (Buxoro viloyati misolida) // Zamonaviy geografik tadqiqotlarda hududlarning ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy va innovasion rivojlanishi, tabiatdan oqilona foydalanish va turizm masalalari xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konfrensiyasi materiallari. 2024 yil. Nukus.
2. Toshbekov N.A., Jamshidov D.R. Buxoro viloyat suv resurslaridan samarali foydalanishning ilmiy asoslari. Экономика и социум. №5(120) 2024.
3. Toshbekov N.A., Jamshidov D.R. Scientific Foundations for the Efficient Use of Water Resources in Bukhara Region. Economics and Society, No. 5(120), 2024.
4. Toshbekov N.A. Issues of Using Collector-Drainage Waters in the Context of Climate Change. In: Proceedings of the International Scientific-Practical Conference on "Climate Change and Its Impact on the Environment: Problems and Solutions". – Tashkent, 2024. – pp. 201–204.
5. Toshbekov N.A., Jamshidov D.R. Prospects for the Development of National Economic Sectors under Global Climate Change in the Aral Sea Basin. In: Proceedings of the International Scientific-Practical Conference. Nukus, 2024. – pp. 149–153.

